

PROCESS-STRUCTURE-PROPERTY RELATIONSHIP FOR ORGANIC SEMICONDUCTORS GROWN BY ORGANIC VAPOR JET PRINTING

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High performance and unique functionality and variety of small molecular organic semiconductors open exciting new opportunities in a variety of applications, including information displays, solar energy harvesting, large-area and ubiquitous electronics, and many others. The growing opportunity for manufacturing scale up in turn requires better control of large-scale processing of thin-film, organic semiconductor devices. This talk will review the application requirements for small molecular organic materials, and relate application requirements to processing methods, outlining the thermophysical and structural properties [1] of organic materials critical to achieving good control over the deposition process.

The Van Der Waals nature of bonding of small molecular organic materials in the condensed state enables rapid, energy-efficient, non-epitaxial vapor-based deposition of device quality films on a variety of low cost substrates. The degree of molecular ordering within the organic films, as well as molecular alignment relative to the substrate, strongly influence charge and energy transport, which impact device performance. For instance, improvements in molecular ordering results in better charge mobility in organic thin film transistors (OTFTs), as well as improved exciton diffusion and charge extraction efficiency in organic solar cells [2,3]. On the other hand, the use of amorphous structure at the donor-acceptor interface in OPVs decreases the interaction between donor and acceptor molecules and minimizes the polaron-pair recombination rate [4] can improve important device performance parameters, such as short circuit current, open circuit voltage, and fill factor – key factors in setting the overall power conversion

efficiency of the solar cell. Thus, a robust and useful thin-film deposition method must enable precise control over the morphology of the films. During film formation, the thermodynamic driving forces that induce nucleation, growth and crystallization of organic semiconductors strongly depend on the kinetic and thermal properties of molecules arriving at substrate surface. In vacuum thermal deposition, for instance, the molecular motion is ballistic, with relatively high kinetic and low thermal energy, usually resulting in amorphous films. In organic vapor phase deposition (OVPD), on the contrary, molecular kinetic energy is low and thermal energy is high due to boundary layer-limited diffusion to the substrate, usually yielding polycrystalline films [1]. Guard-flow organic vapor jet printing (GF-OVJP) technique that utilizes fast carrier gas transport to deliver organic vapor to the substrate in the form of a focused jet, while shielding and focusing the inner jet by an annular inert gas jet. As a result, the molecular velocity and temperature can be tuned across a much wider range, spanning extremes of the deposition regime, allowing much greater latitude in controlling molecular orientation and morphology.

We will show how film properties of small molecular organic materials can be precisely controlled via various deposition process and apparatus parameters, in particular focusing on the novel method of Guard-Flow Organic Vapor Jet Printing (GF-OVJP), [5] and discuss its potential advantages for rapid, additive patterning of electronically active components of organic semiconductor-based devices. Time permitting, we will also demonstrate unique microstructures obtained using GF-OVJP and their potential applications.

References

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